

ISic2741

I.Sicily inscription 2741

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary; magical

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Entella

Place of origin (modern)

Rocca d'Entella

Provenance

Necropolis A, tomb 79

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Contessa Entellina, Museo

Archeologico/Antiquarium Comunale di Entella, inventory E3659

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI339996

1. [ὁ δεῖνα ἐπι] κ,αλει Τακιμα γυναῖκα.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644839

EDCS 64901072

PHI 339996

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 47.1421

Nenci, G. 1997. Novità epigrafiche dall'area elima.

Seconde Giornate Internazionali di studi sull'area elima (Gibellina, 22-26 ottobre 1994). Atti. Pisa. pp. 1187-1202. At 1189 tav.CCXXXIII.2-3

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